

THE CEYLON JOURNAL OF HISTORICAL AND SOCIAL STUDIES

NEW SERIES

Vol. I

July-December 1971

No. 2

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SOUTH INDIAN MERCANTILE COMMUNITIES IN CEYLON, circa 950-1250

K. INDRAPALA

The expansion of Cōla rule from about the middle of the tenth century was followed by the organization of a strong centralised administration resulting in the maintenance of peace for over two centuries over a wide area in South India. The more settled conditions of this period undoubtedly led to considerable economic growth. Clearly the expansion of overseas trade was an important factor in, as well as a reflector of this economic growth. The overseas campaigns of the Cōla emperors in the eleventh century in the Indian Ocean, from the Maldives to the Indonesian Islands, probably had more to do with overseas trade interests than has generally been conceded. Romila Thapar's bold assertion that these campaigns were conducted in order to strike at the Arab competition in the South-east Asian trade and to remove the Śrī Vijayan interference in the Sino-Indian trade may not be far off the mark.¹ The period of Cōla expansion was without doubt a period of the expansion of South Indian commerce; and this is clearly indicated by the occurrence in Burma, Thailand, Indonesia and China of Tamil inscriptions left by some of the more powerful South Indian mercantile communities. The extension of South Indian commerce has not been studied in relation to the overseas expansion of the Cōla power, partly because of the insufficient data that is available at present. Such a study should help to determine the role of commerce in Cōla imperialism. In this paper a preliminary survey of the activities of some of the major South Indian mercantile communities in Ceylon in the period of the Cōla empire has been attempted. It is by no means an exhaustive study of the subject but it is hoped that this will throw a little new light on the still greatly unexplored economic history of ancient Ceylon.

THE BACKGROUND

Towards the ninth century A.D. the major kingdoms of South Asia had developed an extensive commerce and established fairly close relations with West Asia, South-east Asia and China. With the rise of the sea-oriented empire of the Cōlas in the tenth century this commerce as well as South India's relations with other Asian empires, especially China, developed further. At the time the Cōlas were rising to power in South India, the political situation in

1. R. Thapar, *A History of India*, Vol. I (Pelican Books 1968), pp. 195-196.

China became more favourable to the development of closer Sino-Indian trade relations. The Sung government paid particular attention to foreign trade by making it a government monopoly and taking strenuous efforts to increase its volume. Special missions were sent out to entice foreign traders to the shores of China.² It appears that the Cōlas were not slow in grasping these opportunities offered by the Chinese, for we find that Rājarāja I (985-1014), Rājendra I (1012-1044) and Kulottuṅga I (1070-1120) had sent missions to the Chinese court.³ The result was a brisk trade in the eleventh century in textiles, spices and a number of luxury articles. The trade in the luxury articles, however, ran into difficulties in the twelfth century, when the drain of Chinese currency and precious metals resulting from its expansion led to attempts by the Chinese government to restrict the volume of trade with South India.⁴

In the West, South Indian trade with the Persians and the Arabs flourished in a similar manner, although it appears to have been dominated by the West Asians. South Indians were no doubt among the Indian merchants who sailed as far as Kish and Siraf in the Persian Gulf in the tenth, eleventh and twelfth centuries. But their records have not been found in these places and it is not possible to determine the role of the South Indians in this trade from the general references in Arab and Persian literature.

Unlike in contemporary China, trade was not a royal monopoly in South India in the period of Cōla rule. It was purely a private enterprise. But the nature and volume of the trade, both internal and foreign, that developed in South India in this period demanded cooperation among merchants on a bigger scale than there had been before. This kind of cooperation is to be found everywhere in economic life. As in the West of the High Middle Ages, conditions in South India at this time made cooperation indispensable. As Pirenne put it, 'maritime or land trade was possible only by grace of the mutual assurance an association inspired in its members, of the discipline which it imposed upon them, of the regulations to which it subjected them'.⁵ And so we find in the tenth century the emergence of organized mercantile communities, often described as guilds after their Western counterparts, whose strength grew almost parallel to the expansion of Cōla power. Indeed it would appear that the Cōla flag followed the merchant fleets of these communities.

Among the more powerful mercantile communities were the Aiññūruvar (also called the Ayyāvoḷe, Ticai-āyirattu-aiññūruvar and Nānātēciya-ticai-āyirattu-aiññūruvar), the Vira Vaḷañciyar or Vaḷañciyar, the Nānādeśi or Nānātēciyar (sometimes identified with the Aiññūruvar), the Mañigrāmam (or

2. *Chau Ju-kua*, ed. F. Hirth and W. W. Rockhill (Amsterdam 1966), Intro. p. 19.

3. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri, *The Colas* (Madras 1955), pp. 605-606.

4. *Ibid.*, pp. 607-608.

5. H. Pirenne, *Medieval Cities: Their Origins and the Revival of Trade* (5th ed. Princeton 1948), p. 119.

Vaṇikgrāmam) and the Nakarattār.⁶ With them were associated a large number of professional groups and mercenary bodies. They have left behind a considerable number of inscriptions in the South Indian languages and these constitute the main source of our knowledge of their activities.

There is little doubt that the increased volume of internal and foreign trade in the Cōla empire was largely handled by these mercantile communities along with the West Asians. These communities claim in their inscriptions that they carried on their trade activities in a large number of countries and that by land routes and water routes they penetrated into the regions of the six continents.⁷ That these claims were not empty boasts is seen from the fact that their records have been discovered in Ceylon, Burma, Thailand, Indonesia and China, in which places they had established some of their settlements. Already in the ninth century, the Maṇigrāmam had a trading settlement in Takuapa, the ancient Takkola, in Thailand.⁸ In the eleventh century the Nānādeśi had established themselves in Pagan,⁹ Burma, while the Aiññūruvar had gained a foothold in Sumatra, Indonesia.¹⁰ It appears that some of them had ventured even beyond the Straits of Malacca and established themselves at some ports in China.¹¹ And, as Nilakanta Sastri surmises, 'it is possible that small settlements of these traders were found in all important entrepots of the Persian Gulf' as well.¹²

CEYLON

The commercial developments in South India had their natural effects in Ceylon and, from the tenth century, South Indian mercantile communities entered into the island's trade in a more conspicuous manner. The island's internal and foreign trade in the eleventh and twelfth centuries appears to have been much more important and extensive than has been hitherto thought. But in this matter the extant sources cannot give even an approximate idea of the true state of affairs. This is not surprising, for, on the one hand, the monastic and other religious institutions, from which most of our documents, literary as well as epigraphic, emanate, had little to do with trade and, on the other,

6. The transcription of these names is from the Tamil forms but in some cases the more familiar forms (like Nanadesi and Manigramam) have been retained in order to avoid any confusion. For a detailed account of these communities, see A. Appadorai, *Economic Conditions in South India*, Vol. I (Madras 1936), pp. 391-402.
7. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, IV, ed. R. Narasimhachar (Bangalore), Hg. No. 17; VII, Inscr. No. 118 from Shikarpur Taluq.
8. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri, 'The Takuapa (Siam) Tamil Inscription', *Journal of Oriental Research* (Madras), VI, pp. 229-230.
9. E. Hultsch, 'A Vaishnana Inscription at Pagan', *Epigraphia Indica*, VII, p. 197.
10. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri, 'A Tamil Merchant Guild in Sumatra' *Tijdschrift Voor Indische Taal-, Land- en Volken Kunde*, LXXII, 1932 (Batavia), p. 314.
11. J. Filiozat, 'Research in South-east Asia and in the Far East'. *Proceedings of the First International Conference-Seminar of Tamil Studies* (Kuala Lumpur 1968), I, p. 12.
12. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri, *The Colas*, p. 608.

we have only a few documents directly handed down from the merchants and traders. Most of their documents were meant to be records of pious donations to religious institutions rather than documents relating to trade.

The literary sources provide little information on the trade of the island during this period. But we have about thirteen epigraphic records which refer to the activities of the more important South Indian mercantile communities that had come over to Ceylon. In the inscriptions of the earlier period, we get references to the local corporate trading organizations, called *puga* and *nigama*,¹³ but in the records of this period references to indigenous bodies of traders or merchants are sadly lacking. It is, therefore, not known whether there were organized Sinhalese mercantile communities which participated in the trade of the island, especially the overseas trade. Whether the Sinhalese showed little inclination to participate in an organized manner in the overseas trade or not (it is even possible that they could not compete with the foreign merchants), an examination of the inscriptions of the South Indian mercantile communities in the island leaves one with the impression that the Indo-Ceylon trade at least was allowed to fall into the hands of the South Indian mercantile communities, as was the case in the later centuries. Indeed one is tempted to conclude that the Muslim traders from the South Indian ports who established their settlements in the main ports as well as in the market-towns in the interior of the island after the thirteenth century, were only taking over from the earlier Hindu traders from South India.

THE MERCANTILE GROUPS

One of the earliest South Indian mercantile communities to gain a foothold in the island was the Mañigrāmam. In South India its activities extended over a wide area and are referred to in inscriptions from several places in the modern Kerala and Tamilnadu states.¹⁴ These records range from the ninth to the fourteenth century. As noticed earlier, in the ninth century members of this community were engaged in activities in the Thai port of Takua-pa. In Ceylon we get evidence of their activities in the interior market-town of Hopitiḡamu, near Mahiyangana, in the middle of the tenth century. The Badulla Pillar Inscription of Udaya IV (946-954) refers to them as Vanigrāma, a variant

13. S. Paranavitana, *Inscriptions of Ceylon, I, Early Brahmi Inscriptions*, Inserr. Nos. 135, 138, 320, 553, 662, 696a, 726, 1182-1198; S. Paranavitana, 'Tonigala Rock-Inscription', *EZ*, III, p. 181.

14. A. Appadorai, *op. cit.*, pp. 398-402.

form of Maṇigrāmaṃ.¹⁵ This variant form occurs in contemporary Tamil literature as well.¹⁶

The most prominent of the mercantile communities of the eleventh and twelfth centuries was the Aiññūruvar. This community was always associated with a large number of other mercantile and professional groups. In many of their inscriptions from South India as many as forty-six bodies are listed among their associates. This community, therefore, seems to have occupied a supreme position among the professional bodies in the ports and market-towns and acted as their leader, exercising much power and influence over them. Like the kings of that time, they had their own *praśasti* or eulogy, with which most of their records commence. In Ceylon records of this powerful community have been found at Vahalkada, Viharehinna, Padaviya, Ilakkattu-Eba, Ataragalla and Anaulundava. Some of these records contain their eulogy. But this eulogy is a shorter version of the one appearing in their Kannada records in South India.¹⁷ The eulogy is followed by a list of other mercantile and professional bodies which were associated with the Aiññūruvar in the island. This list is not as long as the one in their South Indian records. Among those mentioned in the list are the Vaḷaṅciyar, Nānādeśi, Virakkoṭiyar, Ceṭṭi, Ceṭṭiputtirar, Vaḷaṅkai, Aṅkakkārar, Āvaṅkakkārar, Iḷaṅciṅkam and the Koṅkavālar.

The Vaḷaṅciyar (the Baṅaṅjigas of the Kannada inscriptions) were an influential body among the South Indian communities in Polonnaruva and are mentioned in the Vēḷaikkāra inscription at Polonnaruva as well as in some of the records of the Aiññūruvar.¹⁸ It is not known whether all the Vaḷaṅciyar merchants in Ceylon belonged to one organized group. There was, however, one group of Vaḷaṅciyar merchants who called themselves the Teṅṅilaṅkai Vaḷaṅciyar (the Vaḷaṅciyar of Southern Laṅkā, i.e. Ceylon).¹⁹ The Tanjore District of Tamilnadu was included in the sphere of activity of this group.²⁰

The Nānādeśi community which, like the Vaḷaṅciyar and the Aiññūruvar, seems to have originated in the Kannada country (Mysore State), is mentioned

15. S. Paranavitana, 'A Revised Edition of the Badulla (Horabora) Pillar-Inscription', *Epigraphia Zeylanica (EZ)*, Vol. V (Colombo) p. 182. It is Paranavitana's view that this Vaṅgrāma is the same as Skt. *vaṅig-grāma* and that 'the Tamil *Maṇigrāmaṃ*... is doubtless a corruption of Skt. *vaṅig-grāma*' (Ibid., p. 190, n. 6). The equation of Vaṅgrāma with Maṇigrāma need not be contested, for the alternative form of *vaṅikkirāmaṃ* (also read as *vaṅikakirāmaṃ*) occurs in Tamil literature. The *va* and *ma* do sometimes interchange in the Dravidian languages. Further, the occurrence of this term as a group name in a period when the Maṇigrāmaṃ were active in South India and outside also helps to identify the group as the Maṇigrāmaṃ.
16. *Tolkāppiyam: Naccinārkkīṅiyar Urai*, (Tanjāvar 1962), Peyariyal, *sūtra* II, p. 173.
17. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, X, Inscription No. 170 from Kolar.
18. S. Paranavitana, 'The Polonnaruva Inscription of Vijayabahu I', *Epigraphia Indica*, XVIII, pp. 337-338. The other inscriptions are unpublished.
19. Inscription from Tirukkannapuram, Nannilam Taluk, Tanjore District—*Annual Report on Epigraphy for 1922*, (Madras), Inscr. No. 505, p. 32.
20. The name Teṅṅilaṅkai (Southern Laṅkā) was given to Ceylon to distinguish it from Uttara-Laṅkā (Northern Laṅkā) in South India (Inscr. No. 58 of 1908 in the South Indian epigraphical collection).

in a Sinhalese inscription as well.²¹ Anuradhapura and Padaviya were among the places where they were active. The Virakkotiyyar, who do not appear to have been a very prominent trading body in South India, are mentioned several times in the Ceylonese records.

The Ceṭṭi, who are mentioned in a number of inscriptions, appear to have been a caste of traders, as in modern times, rather than an organized mercantile community. They were traders as well as money-lenders.²² Several place-names in the North-Central Province and the North Western Province have *ceṭṭi* as their first element. These appear to have been the result of Ceṭṭi settlements in the places represented by them and date from the eleventh and twelfth centuries. The Ceṭṭiputrar (literally sons of Ceṭṭi) who are always associated with the Aiññūruvar, may also have been traders, but no evidence is available regarding the nature of their activities.

The Nāṅku-nāṭu (identifiable with the Nālku-nāḍu of the Kannada inscriptions) were among the South Indian mercantile communities that were established in Ceylon before the Cōla conquest. An inscription of the late ninth or the tenth century refers to their activities at Anuradhapura.²³

Among the mercantile communities who were not closely associated with the Aiññūruvar were the Nakarattār (literally, 'Those of the City'). That they were an influential community is known from the Vēlaikkāra inscription at Polonnaruva.

TRADING ACTIVITIES

The evidence of the Ceylonese records of the South Indian mercantile communities is not sufficient to determine the part played by them in the internal and foreign trade of the country. However, the impression that one gets when examining these records is that they played a considerably important role in the trade of the times.

The South Indian inscriptions of these communities refer to their trade in superior elephants, well-bred horses, precious stones of all sorts, spices, perfumes and drugs.²⁴ But their records in Ceylon provide hardly any information on their merchandise. The edict of Parākramabāhu I at Nainativu (Nagadipa), which was addressed to the foreign traders who frequented the port of Urātturai (Sinh. Urātoṭa, modern Ūrkāvururai/Kayts), refers to trading vessels which brought to the king elephants and horses, two of the major commodities in which the

21. D. M. de Z. Wickremasinghe, 'The Slab Inscription Marked D/8 of Queen Lilavati', *EZ*, I, p. 180.

22. A. Appadorai, *op. cit.*, pp. 379-380.

23. *South Indian Inscriptions*, IV, ed. H. Krishna Sastri (Madras 1923), Inscr. No. 1403; K. Indrapala, 'Anurātapurattilulla Nāṅku Nāṭār Kalvetṭu', *Cintamani*, I, No. 4, Jan. 1968 (Peradeniya), pp. 31-35.

24. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, Inscr. No. 118 from Shikarpur Taluq.

Aiññūruvar claim to have traded.²⁵ The horse trade was in all probability in the hands of the Arabs, although references are not lacking in the South Indian inscriptions to 'Ceṭṭi dealers in horses' (*kutiraic-ceṭṭi*).²⁶ Possibly the elephant trade was shared by the South Indians, Sinhalese and South-East Asians. The South Indians possibly had a share in the gem trade as well.

Whatever may have been their role in the foreign trade of the island, these South Indian communities undoubtedly played an important part in the internal trade, and for this there is some evidence in their local records. The fact that all their records have been discovered in the interior, in ancient towns like Anuradhapura, Polonnaruva and Padaviya and in other places, which were also possibly market centres of that time, indicates that they were concerned with the internal trade.

As in many other countries in this period, it appears that the greater part of the internal trade of the island was carried on at fairs and market-towns. These must have been the main channels of commercial intercourse. The South Indian mercantile communities seem to have played a role of some importance in the setting-up and organization of these fairs and market-towns.

In their records there are two important terms which, if clearly understood, are likely to throw an important light on the nature and organization of these centres of trade. These terms occur in the inscriptions of the Aiññūruvar, both in South India and Ceylon. One is *erivira-paṭṭanam*. *Paṭṭana* or *paṭṭanam* stands for a township or city in most of the Indian languages. *Erivīrar* (lit. 'warriors who throw', i.e. those who were adept in the art of throwing javelins, etc.) refers to a class of warriors who were associated with the mercantile communities. *Erivira-paṭṭanam* has been generally interpreted as a 'mercantile town'.²⁷ The records of the Aiññūruvar refer to their declaring certain towns as *Erivira-paṭṭanam*.²⁸ From the context, there is little doubt that these were market-towns, probably protected by the *Erivīrar*. But it must be admitted that there is a lack of clarity as to the nature of these towns. That the South Indian mercantile communities created such towns in Ceylon, too, is known from the Vahalkada inscription. At Vahalkada there was a town named *Kaṭṭanēri* which was declared a 'Nānātēciya-vira-paṭṭanam', where certain measures were taken by the 'Ceṭṭi of the Eighteen Countries and the *Virakkoṭi* so that this town may not be destroyed'.²⁹ Possibly such towns were also set up in the other

25. K. Indrapala, 'The Nainativu Tamil Inscription of Parakramabahu I', *University of Ceylon Review*, XXI, No. 1, April 1963, p. 70.

26. Inscr. No. 556 of 1904 in the South Indian epigraphical collection.

27. T. N. Subramaniam, *South Indian Temple Inscriptions*, III, Part 2 (Madras 1957), Annexure, p. xv.

28. *Annual Report on Epigraphy for 1913*, p. 42, Inscr. No. 342 of 1912 in the South Indian epigraphical collection; *Epigraphia Carnatica*, VIII, p. 89 of the text.

29. Unpublished inscription. The relevant phrases are: *Kaṭṭanēriyāna Nānātēciya-virapaṭṭanam* (line 33) and *Paṭṭinneyyūmi-nāṭṭuc Ceṭṭikaḷum Virakkoṭoyōmum ip-paṭṭana[m] aḷivupaṭāṭākātenru varanmurāi iṭṭamaḷka* (Lines 35-36). *Erivira-paṭṭanam* is sometimes referred as *Virapaṭṭanam*.

places where records of these mercantile communities have been discovered. We do not know how these towns were organized but from the South Indian records we find that each such town had an official called the Paṭṭana-svāmi (Lord of the Town) at its head. It is reasonable to assume that a similar set-up obtained in those Erivira-paṭṭanam created by the Aiññūruvar in Ceylon. These market towns were evidently permanent centres of trade, where a degree of security was ensured by the warrior or mercenary bodies which seem to have protected them.

The other term *tāvaḷam* seems to refer to centres of trade where distribution and exchange took place at periodical gatherings of traders. This term crept into contemporary Sinhalese usage as well, thus providing an indication of the kind of South Indian influence that was felt in the commercial sphere in the island.³⁰ Paranavitana's interpretation of this term as referring to a place where bands of travelling traders halted for exchange of goods seems to be tenable.³¹ As he has pointed out, the Tamil word *tāvaḷakkārar*, meaning 'traders from distant parts' or 'those who keep oxen for carrying burdens', provides a clue to the meaning of the term *tāvaḷam*.³² In the eulogy of the Aiññūruvar found at the beginning of their records from Vahalkada, Padaviya and Viharehinna, there is a reference to the 'sixty-four *kaṭikai tāvaḷam*' and to the '*ceṭṭi* of the *tāvaḷam*' or the '*ceṭṭi* who flourish in the *tāvaḷam*'.³³ These seem to be references to the several *tāvaḷam* set up by the Aiññūruvar.

In the organization of the internal trade of the South Indian communities, the *erivira-paṭṭanam* and *tāvaḷam* may have played a central role. Such trading centres were possibly built by them along their trade routes or were established alongside earlier centres. There is, however, a lack of definite information on this point.

OTHER ECONOMIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE ACTIVITIES

Apart from trade, the other economic activities in which these South Indian communities were engaged are not clearly known. Prosperity in purely mercantile activities resulting in the accumulation of wealth normally leads to banking activities on the part of the successful merchants. These South Indian mercantile communities were no exception to this rule; and we find that at least one of these communities, the Ceṭṭi, were functioning as financiers or money-lenders, an activity for which they became well known in later times.

30. S. Paranavitana, 'Galapata Vihara Rock Inscription', *EZ*, IV, p. 205. The word *tāvaḷama* occurs in modern Sinhalese too. It means 'a number of oxen laden with merchandise' or 'a station on the frontier for the sale or exchange of commodities'.
31. S. Paranavitana, 'Civilisation of the Polonnaru Period: Political, Economic and Social Conditions', *University of Ceylon History of Ceylon*, I, Part 2 (Colombo 1960), p. 550.
32. S. Paranavitana, 'Galapata Vihara Rock Inscription', p. 209, n. 4.
33. Unpublished inscriptions. The relevant phrases are: *Arupattu-nāṅku kaṭikait-tāvaḷamum tāvaḷattu vaḷarkinra Ceṭṭiyum* (Vahalkada, lines 7-8).

A tenth-century inscription refers to such activity on the part of members of the Ceṭṭi community at Anuradhapura.³⁴ It is possible that the other South Indian mercantile communities were also engaged in similar activities.

It is the general view that the king enjoyed the monopoly of minting and issuing coins. There is, however, some evidence in one of the records of the Aiññūruvar which seems to indicate that the South Indian mercantile communities or their associates enjoyed some kind of privilege regarding the minting of coins. The Vahalkada inscription mentioned above refers to an associate of the Aiññūruvar as 'Akkacālai Vikkiramātittaṅ' (Vikkiramātittaṅ of the Mint). It may mean either that this person owned a mint or that he worked at a mint. In either case, it would be difficult to dispute the fact that minting of coins formed one of the activities of some members of the South Indian communities under discussion.

As in Europe during the Middle Ages, when a town protected its citizens by methods which would now be considered appropriate only to a sovereign state, particularly by the use of reprisals, in South India the *erivīra-paṭṭanam* of the, Aiññūruvar protected its residents and conferred certain privileges on them.³⁵ When the Nānādeśi, for instance, converted Kāṭṭūr into a *vīrapaṭṭanam*, they exempted its inhabitants of all communal contributions and declared that the town was 'not to be inhabited by such members of the mercantile classes (1) as demanded taxes or tolls by threatening people with drawn swords or by capturing them and (2) as wantonly deprived people of their food or otherwise afflicted them'.³⁶ It was also resolved that those who offended against this declaration were to be excommunicated.³⁷ It may not be wrong to assume that the *erivīra-paṭṭanam* set up by the South Indian mercantile communities in Ceylon also extended such protection and privileges to their inhabitants. Although the evidence on this point is not adequate, our sources indicate that these South Indian communities in Ceylon did enjoy powers and privileges similar to those enjoyed by the mercantile communities in South India. In South India, for instance, these communities had a share in the collection of tolls, taxes and rates.³⁸ In Ceylon we find that the Nānādeśi enjoyed such a privilege at Anuradhapura. A Sinhalese inscription of the twelfth century informs us that they had a customs-house at Anuradhapura.³⁹ Similarly, the Mañigrāmam seem to have enjoyed the same rights that they enjoyed in South India. The Kottayam Plates of Vīra Rāghava and Sthānu Ravi give details of the honours and

34. K. Indrapala, 'Two Inscriptions from the Hindu Ruins, Anuradhapura', *Epigraphia Tamilica*, I, Part 1, pp. 4-5.

35. T. V. Mahalingam, *South Indian Polity*, (Madras 1955), p. 392.

36. T. V. Mahalingam, *op. cit.*, p. 392.

37. *Ibid.*

38. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, VII, p. 159 of the text; *ARE for 1912*, p. 32, No. 377 of 1911; *ARE for 1919*, pp. 15, 19, Nos. 9 of 1918-19 and 216 of 1918.

39. D. M. de Z. Wickremasinghe, *op. cit.*, p. 180.

privileges enjoyed by the Maṅṅrāmam in Kerala. Among these was a privilege that they had regarding the investigation of crimes. According to the above plates, 'should they themselves commit a crime, they are themselves to have the investigation of it'.⁴⁰ That such a privilege was enjoyed by the Maṅṅrāmam of Hopitiṅgamu in Ceylon is evident from the Badulla inscription.⁴¹

EMPLOYMENT OF MERCENARIES

These mercantile communities were very closely associated with a number of communities given to martial pursuits. Among them were the Eṛivīrar (Warriors who were adept in throwing javelins, etc.), Muṇaivīrar (the Vanguard), Iḷaṅciṅka-vīrar (Warriors with the valour of young lions), Koṅka-vālar (Swordsmen of the Kongu country), Mummuri-daṇḍa (Three-fold Army?) and the well known Vēḷaikkārar. Like the Vēḷaikkārar, probably the others were also mercenaries. They were no doubt employed by the mercantile communities to protect their merchandise, endowments and trust properties. They may be compared to the merchant troops of medieval Europe. Pirenne's conjectural description of these merchant troops may apply equally well to the mercenaries that were employed by the South Indian mercantile communities:

"They should be pictured as armed bands, the members of which, equipped with bows and swords, encircled the horses and wagons loaded with bags, packs and casks.....A chief, the Hansgraf or the Doyen, exercised his authority over the company. This latter was composed of 'brothers', bound together by an oath of fidelity".⁴²

The Vēḷaikkārar and other mercenary troops were bound together, like the company of 'brothers', by an oath of fidelity.⁴³ The Vaḷaṅciyar-cēṅāpati (the Army Commander of the Vaḷaṅciyar Merchants) and the (Nānā)deṣi-daṇḍanāyaka (the Army Commander of the Nānādeṣi Merchants) were probably the counterparts of the Hansgraf or the Doyen.⁴⁴ Apart from employing these mercenaries for protecting themselves and their properties, the mercantile communities appear to have also supplied them to kings and institutions needing the services of the mercenaries.

SOCIAL AND RELIGIOUS ACTIVITIES

Mercantile communities in all countries at all times have been among the leading benefactors of religious institutions as well as agencies by which distress was relieved. Most of the records of the South Indian mercantile communities in the island are those relating to religious grants. These communities

40. A. Appadorai, *op. cit.*, pp. 401-402.

41. S. Parānavitana, 'A Revised Edition of the Badulla (Horabora) Pillar-Inscription, p. 190.

42. H. Pirenne, *op. cit.*, p. 121.

43. S. Parānavitana, 'The Polonnaruva Inscription of Vijayabahu I', p. 337.

44. Unpublished Vahalkada inscription. T. V. Mahalingam, *op. cit.*, p. 393.

figure very prominently among the donors of bells, lamps and money to some of the Hindu temples at Padaviya and elsewhere.⁴⁵ One of the minor mercantile communities, the Nāṅku-nāṭṭār, even helped to erect a Buddhist temple at Anuradhapura.⁴⁶

Erection and maintenance of alms-houses and inns or resting-places were among their other activities which exhibit their care for the unfortunate. In the time of Queen Lilavati (1197-1200, 1209-1210, 1211-1212), for instance, the Nānādeśi used the proceeds from one of their customs-houses for the maintenance of an alms-hall at Anuradhapura with supplies of spice and other requisites.⁴⁷ As in South India, the Aiññūrruvar built inns or resting-places called Aiññūrruvan-ampalam.⁴⁸

These mercantile communities played an important role in the society of the South Indian settlers in the island. As in South India, in Ceylon, too, they were considered to be the leaders of certain other Dravidian communities. In the eleventh and twelfth centuries, and in fact till recent times, the various castes of the Dravidian areas of South India were divided into two major sections, called the Iṭaṅkai (Left Hand) and the Valaṅkai (Right Hand).⁴⁹ These two sections were found in Ceylon, too.⁵⁰ Certain mercantile communities were considered to be the heads or leaders of these sections. In the case of the Valaṅkai the Nānādeśi and the Valaṅciyar were among their leaders, while the Iṭaṅkai had the Nakarattār as one of their leaders.⁵¹ That such a social structure obtained even among the Dravidian communities of Ceylon becomes clear from the Vēlaikkāra inscription at Polonnaruwa. This record states that the Vēlaikkāra troops at Polonnaruwa were drawn from the Valaṅkai, Iṭaṅkai and other sections of the society and that the Valaṅciyar were the leaders of a section of the Vēlaikkāra forces and implies that the Nakarattār were the leaders of another section.⁵²

As the leaders of other Dravidian communities, the mercantile communities enjoyed a prominent position in their society and were invited for important meetings called by the others. There are many instances in the South Indian records of the Aiññūrruvar presiding over meetings at which the affairs of other

45. K. Indrapala, 'An Inscription of the time of Rajaraja I from Padaviya', *Epigraphia Tamilica*, I, Part 1, p. 34. Unpublished inscriptions from Padaviya.

46. *South Indian Inscriptions*, IV, No. 1405; K. Indrapala, 'Anuradapurattilulla Nāṅku Nāṭṭār Kalvettu', p. 35.

47. D. M. de Z. Wickremasinghe, *op. cit.*, p. 180.

48. *South Indian Inscriptions*, IV, No. 1415.

49. B. A. Saletore, *Social and Political Life in the Vijayanagar Empire*, II (Madras 1934), pp. 68 ff.

50. S. Paranavitana, 'The Polonnaruwa Inscription of Vijayabahu I', p. 337.

51. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, XI, p. 61 of the text; *The Imperial Gazetteer of India*, XVIII, pp. 198-199.

52. K. Indrapala, 'Some Medieval Mercantile Communities of South India and Ceylon', *Journal of Tamil Studies*, II, No. 2, Oct. 1970 (Madras), pp. 33-34.

associate communities were settled.⁵³ In Ceylon, the Vaḷaṅciyar and the Nakarattār were invited for meetings of the Vēḷaikkārar and possibly of certain other communities.⁵⁴ It appears that they exercised some degree of control over the activities of the other communities associated with them.

RELATIONS WITH THE STATE

This brings us to the question of their role, if any, in the politics of that time. The economic power of such communities led by necessity to political influence, which the South Indian mercantile communities may have exerted in some instances.

We have seen that the South Indian mercantile communities were closely associated with the mercenary troops in the island. The Vēḷaikkāra army, or some of the component groups in it, considered the Vaḷaṅciyar, and possibly the Nakarattār, to be their leaders. These two mercantile communities were invited for important deliberations of the Vēḷaikkārar. Many other mercenary or warrior groups, like the Eriṅvīrar, Muṅaivīrar, Koṅkavālar, Iḷaṅciṅkavīrar and the Mummuri-daṅḍa, were also closely associated with the mercantile communities and are mentioned often in the records of the latter. In the light of these facts one wonders whether in the eleventh, twelfth and thirteenth centuries mercenary troops were brought to the island from South India by the mercantile communities and supplied to the princes and institutions needing their services. In the period before the ninth century, aspirants to the Sinhalese throne as well as dispossessed rulers often escaped to South India, from where they collected mercenary troops and came over to the island to capture power or to regain the throne.⁵⁵ But in the period after the ninth century, the local sources do not refer to such instances of mercenary troops being brought by Sinhalese royalty. Yet, there were mercenaries in the employ of the Polonnaruva kings and they were a powerful factor in the politics of the day. The Vēḷaikkāra army in particular wielded much influence in the reign of Vijayabahu I (1055-1110) and later.⁵⁶ There were occasions when it rose against the king.⁵⁷ Considering the relationship that existed between the mercenaries and the mercantile communities at this time, it appears that the former were brought to the island by the latter. This may be one reason why the Vēḷaikkārar, or at least an important section of this army, looked up to the Vaḷaṅciyar merchants as their leaders. The activities of the mercenaries seem to have had the sanction and guidance of the mercantile communities. If this were true, the

53. *Epigraphia Carnatica*, VII, p. 159 of the text.

54. S. Paranavitana, 'The Polonnaruva Inscription of Vijayabahu I', p. 337.

55. *Mahāvamsa*, ed. W. Geiger (Colombo 1950), 35:26, 27; 36:49; *Cūlavamsa*, ed. W. Geiger (Colombo 1953), 44:71, 105, 125, 129, 152, 45:18, 47:33-36, 46-57.

56. *Cūlavamsa*, 66:36; 63:24; 74:44.

57. *Ibid.*, 60:36; 74:44.

mercantile communities could be said to have exercised some degree of political influence through the mercenaries. In the absence of any direct evidence bearing on this point, one has to confine oneself to mere speculation.

For the greater part of this period, the relations between the state and these mercantile communities were most likely cordial. In view of the financial benefits which the ruler derived from the commercial transactions of these foreign mercantile communities, he was naturally interested in their protection and in the furtherance of their activities. Thus we find that Parākramabāhu I issued an edict inviting foreign merchants to trade in his ports and guaranteeing them protection.⁵⁸ This probably shows that there was no serious rivalry between the Sinhalese and foreign traders, at least in the twelfth century, and that foreign merchants enjoyed the protection of the state.

Yet the activities of such communities were naturally dependent on a high degree of political stability. As long as there was stability they could flourish and develop their trade. Such a stability was there in Ceylon till the end of the twelfth century. But from the end of that century the political upheavals that took place in the island and the consequent division of the island into a northern kingdom controlled mainly by foreigners and a south-western kingdom ruled by the Sinhalese must have seriously affected the activities of the South Indian mercantile communities. What part they played in the politics of the thirteenth century is not known. But their activities possibly provided the economic background to the rise of the northern kingdom, whose power and prosperity depended on the control of the overseas trade.

The political upheavals of the thirteenth century, both in South India and Ceylon, undoubtedly affected their activities in the Sinhalese kingdom, where their records are not found after the thirteenth century. The growing Arab competition was possibly an additional factor which brought about their decline and the final disappearance of their trade in the Sinhalese kingdom. Their activities perhaps continued a little longer in the northern kingdom.

58. K. Indrapala, 'The Nainativu Tamil Inscription of Parakramabahu I', p. 70.